

EdiCitNet News Template

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

EdiCitNet News

Dear all,

Please share the information related to your news using this template. We will use this information to produce news on the Website.

Don't forget to share at least one picture, to make the news more inviting.

News Information

* **News Title:** Please enter here a news title (Example: City Team Meeting in Berlin; EdiCitNet Workshop in Oslo, etc.)

Feel free to be creative !!!

Text of 30 to 150 characters will be accepted

EdiCitNet toolbox web is already available in 7 different languages

* **Description:** Please enter here the text related to the news you are sharing. It can be a local event, meeting or other, related to Edible City Solutions (ECS) and/or EdiCitNet in your cities.

Text of 500 to 2500 characters will be accepted

In order to make the EdiCitNet toolbox web more inclusive and user friendly, ICRA, UL, SEMIDE and BOKU are joining efforts to translate the web into 7 different languages: English, Catalan, Portuguese, French, Spanish, Slovenian and German. The whole web is translated, except the sections that are under construction.

WP2 would like to include as many languages as possible. Therefore, if you want to see the EdiCitNet toolbox web in your own language, please contact us, we will be very glad to give you guidance on the translation procedure.

Feature Image: Please send an image that will be displayed together with the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

222073b8-e562-439c-b196-ee7d2fcd03ac/Captura_de_pantalla_2020-12-15_095205.png

Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

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Hereby I confirm we have the rights to share this picture in EdiCitNet news.

URL: Here you can share an URL related to the news like a link to a video, website, etc.

<https://toolbox.edicitnet.com/>

Date: Please confirm the date of the news you are sharing.

10/12/2020

Please specify a location related to the news you are sharing. (City, Address, Venue, etc.)

500 character(s) maximum

Contact Person

* **First and last Name:** Please enter your complete name. It will be displayed as author of the news.

Joana Castellar

* **Organisation:** Please enter the name of your organisation.

Institut Català de Recerca de l'Aigua (ICRA)

* **Position:** Please indicate your position in your organisation.

Research Technician

* **City & Country:** Please indicate the city and country where you are contacting us from.

Girona - Spain

* **Email:** Your email will not be shown in the news, unless you explicitly indicate it below. We will use it to contact you if we have any question.

jcastellar@icra.cat

I want my Email to be displayed in the news.

- Yes
 No

Social Media

* I agree to share my news on the EdiCitNet Twitter and/or Instagram

- Yes, both of them
 No, none of them
 Only on Twitter
 Only on Instagram

Additional Comments:

500 character(s) maximum

Contact

puerta@arttic.eu

